

The Influence of The Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) Cooperative Learning Model on Class III Student Learning Outcomes Theme 1 Subtheme 1 at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to see the effect of the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model on the learning outcomes of third grade students of Theme 1 Subtheme 1 at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar. The research method used is Quantitative with Pre-experimental Designs research type and One-Group Pretest-Posttest research design. The research population was class III UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar as many as 23 people. The data collection technique is in the form of pretest and posttest tests. By conducting the pretest stage, giving treatment by applying the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model and posttest, research data is generated. The average pretest score is 61.09 which is included in the poor category or has not met the KKM, then the average posttest score is 76.09 which is included in the good category. Based on the results of data analysis and hypotheses tested, it is known that the cooperative learning model of the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type has an effect on student learning outcomes. This is evidenced by the results of the t test with the type of paired sample t-test statistical test obtained the price of t_{hitung} which is 6.617 with a frequency (db) of $23 - 1 = 22$, at a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$ obtained t_{table} which is 2.074 Then obtained $t_{hitung} > t_{table}$ or $6.617 > 2.074$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means the hypothesis in this study H_a is accepted. Thus, the cooperative learning model of the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type affects the learning outcomes of third grade students of Theme 1 Subtheme 1 at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state (Sisdiknas, 2003). Education plays a very important role in forming the nation's next generation of young people who are capable, intelligent and reliable in implementing the development of national life. In accordance with Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education system, article 3 (National Education System, 2003) states that:

"National Education functions to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate the life of the nation, aiming to develop the potential of students to become human beings who are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become Democratic and responsible citizens."

Seeing the important role of education in forming the nation's next generation, improving the quality of education is something that must be done on an ongoing basis in order to keep up with developments over time. In line with the times, to make Indonesian education higher quality, the government has decided to make changes or changes to the curriculum in order to improve the learning process activities in every school unit in Indonesia. The change from the KTSP curriculum to the 2013 Curriculum creates a generation that is ready to face future challenges or able to compete. The 2013 curriculum places more emphasis on students being able to observe, ask questions, reason, and be able to present what students know after receiving learning from the teacher. Especially at the elementary school level (SD/MI), the implementation of learning uses an approach called integrated or what we are familiar with, namely thematic learning.

Learning is integrated learning where implementation is carried out through the principles of learning using themes. In implementing thematic learning there must be a successful learning process obtained from the learning which is called learning outcomes. These learning outcomes can be taken from the assessment process. The assessment process is taken from learning activities between teachers and students. Thematic learning learning outcomes are the abilities that students gain after the learning process takes place to gain learning experience which is shown in their behavior, increasing knowledge, and having skills.

Based on the explanation above, an innovative learning model is needed for these students. Several types of models that can be used for good learning activities in the classroom are cooperative learning models, PBL, contextual learning, and simulation role playing. To fix the problems in the class, a learning model is needed to fix all of this. One model that can make students more active is the STAD type cooperative learning model.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Learning model is something pattern process used _ as guidelines in plan activity learning . Learning is something nature activities _ systematic . That means learning is something consisting of activities from various components , such as objective learning ; fill And material learning ; experience learning , which includes method learning , media, allocation time And place learning ; as well as evaluation results learning . All matter the need designed in a way systematically so that everything business learning can done in a way effective And efficient (Setiawan , 2018:34). According to Shoimin state that , put forward a learning model is framework conceptually descriptive _ systematic procedures _ in organize experience Study For reach objective Study certain , and works as guidelines for para designer learning And para teacher in plan activity Study teaching .Based on opinion on can taken conclusion that , learning model relate with not quite enough the teacher answers to planning , implementing , and evaluate activity learning . Success from something activity learning Also No regardless from the model used by the teacher while inside class .

Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) developed by Robert Slavin and colleagues at John Hopkins University and is the simplest cooperative approach . Teachers use STAD, also refers to student group learning, presenting information new academics to students every week using verbal presentation or text. Huda stated that Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) is a cooperative learning strategy in which several small groups of students with different levels of academic ability work together to complete learning objectives. While Hosnan's application, the STAD model is used to develop cooperative, creative, think critical , and There is will to help friends and also as a learning experience cooperative Which The simplest. Based on several theoretical opinions above, the author can conclude that The STAD learning model is a type of learning model cooperative Which The simplest way is to use small groups each Its members consist of 4-5 people heterogeneously, consisting of men and women women, coming from various tribes, have abilities high, medium, and low to help each other in completing learning given by the teacher.

In every model for sure own a number of excess And weakness . According to Shoimin has the advantage of the Student Team s Achievement Division s model (STAD) namely :

- a) Student Work The same in reach objective with uphold tall norms group
- b) Student active help And motivating Spirit For succeed together .
- c) Active role as a peer tutor For more increase success group .
- d) Interaction between student along with enhancement ability they in opinion .
- e) Increase proficiency individual .
- f) Increase proficiency group .
- g) No nature competitive .
- h) No have a sense of revenge .

Above the author already explained excess from the Student Team s Achievement Division s (STAD) model . So researcher Also must explained weakness from this model . According to Shoimin (2014:189) states that the weaknesses of the STAD model are as following :

- a) Contributions from low achieving students become less.
- b) High achieving students will lead to disappointment because of the role Smart members are more dominant.
- c) It takes longer for students so it is difficult to achieve curriculum targets.
- d) It takes longer so teachers generally don't want to using cooperative learning.
- e) Requires special abilities so not all teachers can carry out cooperative learning.
- f) Demand certain characteristics from students, for example the nature of liking to work together .

METHODS

This research is a quantitative research method, with Pre-experimental Designs research type. . This research is a One Group Pretest-Posttest Design type of research . With this research, the results of the treatment can be known more accurately, because it can be compared with the situation before treatment and after treatment. This research was conducted at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar which is located at Jl. Farel Pasaribu No. 76, Sukamaju, District. Siantar Marihat, Pematang Siantar City, North Sumatra Province. This research was carried out in the even semester of FY 2023/2024. The researcher chose this location because to the researcher's knowledge no one had conducted research with the same title at that school. The population in this study were all 23 class III UPTD students at SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar. The instrument used in this research is a test instrument. The written test instrument is a multiple choice test. The test consists of 20 questions. To determine the feasibility of the test to be tested, researchers use validity tests, reliability tests, level of difficulty and distinguishing power . The data analysis techniques used in this research are:

- Normality test
the Kolmogorov-Smirnov-Shapiro normality test is used .
- Hypothesis testing
Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether there are significant average differences in data. The hypothesis test used in this research is the t-test . Researchers used SPSS Windows 21 , the t-test used was the paired sample t-test . The criteria for determining the significance of data are data with a probability of significance > 0.05 , then H_a is accepted. Data with a probability of significance < 0.05 , then H_0 is rejected.

To determine the decision rule, namely:

- a) If $t_{\text{Count}} > t_{\text{Table}}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that the Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) type cooperative

learning model influences the learning outcomes of class III students in theme 1 subtheme 1 at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar.

- b) If $t_{\text{Count}} < t_{\text{Table}}$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, meaning that the Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) type cooperative learning model has no effect on the learning outcomes of class III students in theme 1 subtheme 1 at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar.
- c) Look for the t table using the t distribution table with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $dk = N - 1$.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This research is a pre-experimental design research with a one group pretest posttest design. Where students are given a pretest and posttest. The pretest is given before the treatment, the aim is to find out the initial condition of the students before being given the treatment. The posttest is given after the learning material is given using the Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) type cooperative learning model, the aim is to find out the final condition of the students given the treatment.

Testing is carried out by calculating the calculated r value if the calculated r value of the instrument can be used for data collection, and the instrument used for data collection by researchers uses validation with a significant level using validation with a level of 5% or 0.05 where 25 levels. Based on the excel results, it was found that the number of questions that could be used for the next question was 20 questions.

From the results of the reliability test calculations, it can be concluded that the results of the reliability test for this research are 0.81 (can be said to be reliable). Analysis of the level of difficulty of the items used is used to test the test questions in terms of their difficulty so that it can be obtained which questions fall into the difficult, medium and easy categories (it can be said that medium questions = 21, easy questions = 4). The discriminating power of the questions is the ability of the questions to differentiate between groups of students with high and low scores. To calculate the differentiating power, the tests are grouped into two, namely the upper group and the lower group.

This descriptive analysis is used to describe the data from each research variable. The independent variable in this research is the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model, while the dependent variable in this research is the learning outcomes of class III students in theme 1 subtheme 1 at UPTD SD Negeri 125 543 Pematang Siantar.

The normality test is intended to find out whether the data used is distributed or not. Testing this hypothesis using the t test is used to test the level of significance of the partial influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test is carried out by comparing the calculated $t > t$ table and the significant value of the dependent variable. Basis for collecting decisions:

- a) If $\text{sig} > 0.05$ then the data is normally distributed
- b) If $\text{sig} < 0.05$ then the data is not distributed

In this section, the results found in the research that have been carried out will be described. The results in question are the conclusions drawn based on the data collected and the data analysis that has been carried out. Based on the pretest results, the average student learning outcome score was 61.09 with 19 students scoring below the KKM and 4 students completing the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model relatively low.

Furthermore, the average value of the posttest results was 76.09. So, after using the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model students have better learning outcomes than before using the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) learning model. After carrying out the pretest and posttest normality tests, the hypothesis t test was carried out. Based on the hypothesis t test, it was found that $t = 6.617$ with a significant level (2-tailed) of 0.000, the probability was significant < 0.05 , $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table} = 6.617 > 2.074$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model on the learning outcomes of class III UPTD students at SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the data presented in the previous section, the researcher concluded that the student learning outcomes before being given treatment, all students still had not reached the KKM, namely 19 students (100%) and after being given treatment, student learning outcomes increased, namely 19 students (100%). % has a value above the KKM and is based on the results of hypothesis testing with a significance level = 0.05 and t table of 2.047, t count of 6.617. Thus ($t \text{ count} > t \text{ table } 6.617 > 2.047$), it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) type cooperative learning model on the learning outcomes of class III UPTD students at SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar.

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